

Adsorption of Propionic Acid at Mercury-Solution Interface from KCl and KBr Solutions—Part II.

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Free energies of adsorption for propionic acid on mercury from KCl and KBr solutions are evaluated and shown to be dependent on the charge of the electrode. This is shown to be due to dipole-dipole interaction in the electrical double layer. Charge components in the double layer are evaluated and it is shown that the adsorption of the acid takes place as a competitive process.

Electrocapillary data for the adsorption of propionic acid from KCl and KBr aqueous solutions at mercury-solution interface have already been given in Part I¹ and the dependence of surface excess of the acid on electrode potential and on the concentration of organic acid has been discussed. In the present paper, free energies of adsorption of propionic acid have been evaluated to examine the interaction of the adsorbed molecules at the interface. An attempt has been made to analyse the charge components of the double layer in presence of organic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Using similar experimental set up and procedure as in Part I, electrocapillary data were obtained for (a) different concentrations of KCl in 0.526 *M* propionic acid and for (b) different concentrations of KBr in 0.4687 *M* propionic acid. The electrocapillary curves obtained for these systems are shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Charge components in the double layer :

The surface excess of K^+ ions can be evaluated as

$$\Gamma_{K^+} = - \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial \mu_{KCl}(\text{or } KBr), E^-, \mu_{org.}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where γ is the interfacial tension, μ the chemical potential of the given species, E^- the potential measured with an electrode reversible to Cl^- (or Br^-) ions dipping in the same experimental solution. The potentials measured with reference to saturated calomel electrode were corrected to the E^- scale by actually measuring the potentials of the cells of the type and applying the suitable correction.

Sat. calomel electrode	Experimental solution	$Hg_2Cl_2(S)$
	containing Cl^- (or Br^-)	or
	ions.	$Hg_2Br_2(S)$
		Hg

Equation (1) allows one to evaluate the Γ_{K^+} values from the slopes of the plot of γ versus $RT \ln a_{salt}$ at a given value of E^- . These were converted to charge density per sq. cm. of the interface by multiplying with the value of Faraday. The standard deviation in our graphical computation of surface charge values was estimated as $\pm 0.05\mu$ coulomb/cm².

Since for each of the solutions namely (1) 0.1 M KCl in 0.526 M propionic acid and (2) 0.1 M KBr in 0.4687 M propionic acid, the value of the surface charge at various potentials is known (Part I), and as

$$q^M = -q^s = q_{K^+} + q_{Cl^-(\text{or } Br^-)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where q^s is the charge in microcoulombs cm⁻² on the solution side of the double layer, charge due to Cl^- ions (or Br^- ions) at the interface could be determined.

Fig. 3. Charge components at the double layer for 0.1 M KCl and 0.526 M Propionic acid. $q_d^{K^+}$ and $q_d^{Cl^-}$ are charges due to K^+ and Cl^- ions in the diffuse layer, q^s the total charge, $q_{Cl^-}^s$ charge due to Cl^- in the double layer, $q_{Cl^-}^s$ charge due to specifically adsorbed Cl^- ion. Γ_{acid} surface excess of acid (right hand scale).

Fig. 4. As in Fig. 3 for 0.1 M KBr + 0.4687 M Propionic acid.

As K^+ ions are known not to be specifically adsorbed, the corresponding charge due to Cl^- (or Br^-) ions in the diffuse double layer can be obtained from computed tables². The charge due to specifically adsorbed Cl^- or Br^- ions can then be obtained as the difference of the total excess charge due to halide ions and the charge in the diffuse layer for the mixed solutions mentioned above. The surface excess due to propionic acid has already been obtained (Part I). Fig. 3 and 4 give these charge components and organic acid adsorbed as a function of E^- and thus show a complete 'material profile' at the interface. Table I brings out the contributions due to cations and specifically adsorbed anions in presence and absence³ of organic adsorbate, at three different q^s values.

3. J. Lawrence and R. Parsons, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, 16, 193.

TABLE I

q 's are in μ -coulombs cm^{-2} , 'i' represents inner layer, d-diffuse layer.

	$q^s = +8$		$q^s = 0$		$q^s = -4$	
	K^+	Br^-	K^+	Br^-	K^+	Br^-
	q_a	q_i	q_a	q_i	q_a	q_i
KBr	+6.8	-0.2	+3.7	-4.9	+4.5	-9.8
KBr+Propionic acid	+7.7	-1.1	+1.8	-2.7	+2.8	-7.9

It is seen from this table that the negative charge contributions due to anions (q_i^-) with propionic acid in solution is less than that for pure KBr solution. Similar observations have also been observed for KCl+propionic acid system. Bockris *et al.*⁴ have observed this behaviour for systems containing HCl and Phenol. It is clear, therefore, that the adsorption of organic compounds results in decrease in the number of specifically adsorbed halions at the interface. The decrease in the anionic charge of 2.2μ coulombs cm^{-2} at $q^s = 0$ corresponds to 1.4×10^{13} bromide ions/ cm^2 approximately. The adsorption of propionic acid which contains a dipole in the $-\text{COOH}$ group is 3.0×10^{-10} moles cm^{-2} i.e., about 18×10^{13} molecules cm^{-2} . It appears therefore, that at $q^s = 0$, there is a replacement of about 12 dipoles for one bromide ion less at the electrode. Though this figure is large, it is reasonable to believe the replacement of one halide by a number of dipoles.

2. Esin and Markov Effect⁵:

Esin and Markov relation is given by⁶

$$\frac{1}{RT} \left[\frac{\partial E^-}{\partial \ln a_{\text{acid}}} \right]_{\text{T,P,q}^M, \mu_{\text{KCl (or KBr)}}} = - \left[\frac{\partial \Gamma_{\text{acid}}}{\partial q^M} \right]_{\text{T,P}, \mu} \quad \dots (3)$$

Fig. 5. Esin-Markov plots for $0.1 M$ KBr+Propionic acid (dotted line) and $0.1 M$ KCl+Propionic acid (full line).

4. E. Blomgren, J.O'M. Bockris and C. Jesh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 2000.

5. D. C. Grahame, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **6**, 337.

6. R. Parsons, Proc. 2nd Int. Congress Surface Activity, Butterworths, London, 1957, **3**, 38.

Fig. (5) shows the variation of E^- with $\log C$ at constant charge where C is the concentration of the acid. It is seen from these curves that the slopes of the lines change with charge density. The significance of the above relation is clear that a zero slope of the plot corresponds to q^M value at which the adsorption is maximum for all the concentrations of a given substance. The value obtained from these plots is -2 microcoulombs/cm², which is in agreement with the observation made from the study of free energy dependence of adsorption on charge brought out in the next section.

3. Free energy of adsorption :

The process of adsorption of an organic compound may be considered as a replacement of water molecules at the interface by it^{7,8}. Thus,

where n is the number of water molecules displaced by one organic molecule. The standard free energy of adsorption referred to unit mole fraction of water in solution is

$$\Delta \bar{G}^\circ = -2.303 RT \log \left[\frac{55.5}{C_{\text{org}}} \cdot \frac{\theta}{(1-\theta)^n} \frac{[\theta + n(1-\theta)]^{n-1}}{n^n} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

where θ represents the coverage given by $\Gamma/\Gamma_{\text{max}}$, being the number of moles required for complete coverage. Assuming the cross sectional area⁹ of propionic acid as 21 \AA^2 , standard free energy of adsorption was computed using IBM 1620 computer, with $n = 2.18$ at different values of E^- for different concentrations of acid in $0.1 M$ KCl and KBr. Keeping in view that the fundamental variable in electroadsorption is the charge and not the potential¹⁰, the

Fig. 6. Free energy of adsorption as a function of charge density. Dotted line for solutions containing KBr, full line for KCl. ■ $-0.228 M$, × $-0.296 M$, S $0.468 M$, ▲ $-0.728 M$, ⊙ $-1.07 M$, ⊖ $-1.479 M$, ▲ $-2.011 M$, □ $-3.04 M$ Propionic acid.

7. J. O'M. Bockris, M. A. V. Devanathan and K. Muller, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1963, **A-274**, 55.

8. J. O'M. Bockris and D. A. J. Swinkels, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1964, **111**, 736.

9. N. K. Adam, *Physics and Chemistry of Surfaces*, Chapter III, Oxford Univ. Press. London, 1941.

10. R. Parsons, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 136; 1964, **8**, 93.

variation of free energy with charge is shown in Fig. 6. It is observed from the plot that the free energy varies with q^M which is an indication that electrostatic effects are involved in the process of adsorption. It is observed that maximum adsorption for all concentrations occurs at $q^M = -2\mu$ coulombs cm^{-2} .

For the dependence of free energy of adsorption on the extent of coverage, Conway and Barradas¹¹ introduced a surface activity coefficient, f_θ , given by

$$f_\theta = \exp (G^1)_\theta / RT \quad \dots (5)$$

where $(G^1)_\theta$, the non-ideal free energy is given by

$$(G^1)_\theta = \frac{1}{2} Nn \left[\frac{\mu^2 \theta^{3/2}}{\epsilon_s \pi^{3/2} r^3} - 1190 \frac{Z h \theta^3}{\epsilon_0 \pi^3 r^{3/2}} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

where N refers to one mole of the adsorbed molecules, n the coordination number of the species adsorbed, μ the dipole moment of the solute molecule, ϵ_0 and ϵ_s the dielectric constants of the solvent in the surface layer and the dielectric constant of surface layer respectively, r the radius of the organic adsorbate and Z the number of electrons in the outermost electronic shells of the molecule. Neglecting θ^3 in comparison with $\theta^{3/2}$ at $\theta < 0.6$, according to (6), a linear plot of $\Delta \bar{G}^0$ against $\theta^{3/2}$ should be realised at constant charge. This is brought out in Fig. 7 where the two lines are for different base electrolytes and the points are for different values of q^M . It is obvious that a linear relationship is realised in both cases with identical slope. This is to be expected as the adsorption of the same organic compound is taking place in both cases.

Fig. 7. Variation of free energy of adsorption with $\theta^{3/2}$. Charge density in microcoulombs cm^{-2}

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